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**НАЦІОНАЛЬНА АКАДЕМІЯ НАУК УКРАЇНИ
ІНСТИТУТ ПРОБЛЕМ МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ В ЕНЕРГЕТИЦІ
ім. Г.Є. ПУХОВА НАН УКРАЇНИ**

**МАТЕРІАЛИ
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THE ROLE OF THE HUMAN FACTORS FOR THE RESILIENCE OF DYNAMIC SYSTEMS

Unlike technical systems, socio-technical systems are more complex to understand due to their intangible causes and the intricate relationships between these causes and their effects. Leveraging human adaptability and strengths can significantly improve a dynamic system's resilience, recovery, and safety. Human factors have traditionally been viewed as liabilities, with a focus on human weaknesses. This socio-technical complexity makes it challenging to enhance the resilience of European physical and critical infrastructures against a wide range of large-scale disruptions.

In 2025, the European Union (EU) launched the call HORIZON-CL3-2025-01-INFRA-02, which emphasizes the role of human factors in enhancing the resilience of critical infrastructure ^[1]. Within Horizon Europe Cluster 3 – Civil Security for Society, the goal is to improve infrastructure resilience against civil security threats through interdisciplinary research. The Horizon fund provides five million euros per project, categorized as an innovation action (IA), which can include cross-border cooperation across multiple countries or sectors. The EU taxonomy related to human factors is based on taxonomies derived from scientific studies and a set of standards, including ^[2]. A core element of Horizon, the EU encourages interdisciplinary research by integrating Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) with Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) ^[3]. The report shows that 88% of current EU projects include at least one SSH partner, while STEM partners constitute 78% of all partners. The United States (US) has a long-standing tradition of managing human factors, also called 'ergonomics.' Human Factors combines ideas from disciplines like psychology, anatomy and physiology, social sciences, engineering, design, and organizational management. It merges these areas to improve understanding of how socio-technical systems interact. These systems, along with their operational contexts, encompass people, products, technology, organizations, and environments. Here are the selected standards and regulations ^{[4][5][6]}.

The Pukhov Institute for Modelling in Energy Engineering (PIMEE), in collaboration with Mykolas Romeris University (MRU) and as part of the Impress-U project consortium, continues its research and has identified key gaps: (i) inadequate alignment between human and technological factors; (ii) a high level of autonomy, or silos, between technological and human practices, which hinders innovation; (iii) a mismatch in the maturity levels of technologies, skills, regulations, law enforcement, and research programs. Additionally, the author argues that human-technological systems should not only become more resilient, achievable, and nuanced through the integration of the prepare, absorb, recover, and adapt phases, but also that critical systems should become threat-agnostic in dynamic environments ^[7]. The author recommends the following measures:

1. Create Cross-Disciplinary Platforms.

The US Department of Transportation (DoT) has founded the Human Factors Coordinating Committee (HFCC), which serves as a multi-modal team with government-wide liaisons to promote human factors and to address crosscutting human factors issues in transportation. A working group led by the US Department of Defence (DoD) includes a total of 38 members as of 2019, from the Air Force - 2, Army - 1, Navy - 4, Department of Energy (DoE) - 10, Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) - 1, National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) - 4, Industry - 10, and Academia - 6. The North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) developed Network Enabled Capabilities (NEC), enabling platforms and Command and Control (C2) systems to integrate with Human System Integration (HSI). HSI considers human abilities and limitations in system definition, design, development, and evaluation to enhance overall system performance in operational environments. Overall, it is part of a comprehensive systems engineering approach to analysis, design, development, and testing for key decision-makers in the defence sector (e.g., war fighters, policymakers, capability developers, acquisition managers, systems engineers). A similar approach could be effective for stakeholders across public, private, and civil sectors in many fields.

2. Achieve The Human Readiness Level (HRL), Technology Readiness Level (TRL), and Manufacturing Readiness Level (MRL) Alignment

American National Standards Institute (ANSI), together with the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society (HFES), developed a standard, HFES 400. The standard defines nine levels of the Human Readiness Level (HRL) scale and guides the application of the HRL scale in existing systems engineering and human systems integration (HSI) processes. The HRL mirrors the existing Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and Manufacturing Readiness Level (MRL) scale and is designed to evaluate, track, and communicate a technology's readiness for human use. It fully incorporates the human element throughout the entire system lifecycle. Table 1 provides a unified view of the alignment between HRL, TRL, and MRL across various development phases, highlighting the integration of human, technological, and manufacturing readiness.

Table 1. - The Human Readiness Level (HRL), Technology Readiness Level (TRL), and Manufacturing Readiness Level (MRL) Alignment

Level	Phase	TRL	HRL	MRL
1	R&D	Basic Principles Observed/ Reported	Basic Human Research	Basic Manufacturing Implications and Studies
2	R&D	Technology Concept and Application	Design Guidelines	Manufacturing Concepts Identified
3	R&D	Analytical or Experimental Proof	Requirements for Human	Manufacturing Proof of Concept
4	T&D	Components in a	Modeling,	Prototype

		Laboratory	Part-Task, Studies	Components in a Laboratory
5	T&D	Components Demonstrated	Evaluation of Prototypes	Prototype Components - a Production-Relevant
6	P&D	System Model or Prototype Operational	Design Fully Matured	Subsystems in a Prototype
7	P&D	Completed Through Prototype Tests	Design Fully Tested	Subsystems/ Components in a Production Design
8	P&D	Completed Through Actual Systems Tests	Design Verified /Approved	Pilot Line, Manufacturing Proven
9	P&D	Proven Through Actual System Operation	Operational Use and Monitoring	Low Rate Production
10	FRP	N/A	N/A	Full Rate Production

R&D: Research and Development, T&D: Technology Demonstration, P&D: Production and Deployment. The author’s assessment refers to ANSI/HFES ^{[8][9]}.

3. Develop Human Factors in Modelling and Studies

These studies demand significant time and resources, making careful planning essential to ensure a positive human impact and prevent human errors with serious consequences. Practical frameworks can be proposed, such as the HUNTER (Human Unimodel for Nuclear Technology to Enhance Reliability)—a computation-based human reliability analysis framework developed by the US Department of Energy (DoE). The Human Factors Analysis and Classification System (HFACS) is a framework used for analyzing and categorizing human errors in incidents ^[10]. It aims to explain why incidents occur through hierarchical taxonomies. Conversely, HUNTER^[11] employs quantitative models that incorporate system and human dynamics. The modelling, data collection, measurement, metrics, training, operational, legal, and ethical aspects are discussed in works^{[12][13][14][15]}.

As sub-modules of design, the ‘human factors for’ (HF4) dynamic systems will help researchers integrate HF4Resilience, HF4Recovery, HF4Energy, HF4Modelling, HF4Cyber, HF4Hesma, and others to ensure the resilience of critical infrastructure in a changing environment. Empirical studies remain key milestones for human factors’ role surveys, case studies, or controlled experiments.

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